

Supplementary Material

Effect of pressure on the carbon dioxide hydrate – water interfacial free energy along its dissociation line

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I. TIME EVOLUTION OF NUMBER OF WATER MOLECULES IN HYDRATE

According to the main article, we have determined the time evolution of n_h , the number of water molecules in the CO₂ hydrate slab, at three different pressures along its dissociation line. Figs. 1, 2, and 3 show n_h , as a function of time, at 100 bar for r_w ranging from 0.697 to 1.235 Å. Fig. 4 shows n_h , as a function of time, at 400 bar for r_w ranging from 0.918 to 1.203 Å. And finally, Figs. 5 and 6 show n_h , as a function of time, at 1000 bar for r_w ranging from 0.887 to 1.267 Å.

In all cases, it is possible to identify three different scenarios, as defined in our previous works^{1,2}: (a) Scenario I, in which none of the trajectories exhibits induction period and system always crystallizes if simulation runs are sufficiently long (no free energy barrier between the fluid and solid phases exists); (b) Scenario II, in which at least one trajectory shows an induction period, i.e., n_h does not grow, on average, from $t = 0$ ns; and (c) Scenario III, in which none of them exhibit, on average, monotonic increasing of n_h with time due to the existence of a free energy barrier between the fluid and solid that does not allow the system to crystallize. As can be seen, there exists a minimum value of r_w for which at least one of the trajectories shows an induction period at different pressures: (a) 100 bar for $r_w \geq 0.855$ Å (see Fig. 1); (b) 400 bar for $r_w \geq 0.950$ Å (see Fig. 4); and 1000 bar for $r_w \geq 0.982$ Å (see Fig. 5).

FIG. 1. Number of water molecules in the crystal slab, n_h , as function of time for several trajectories and different well radius, r_w (as indicated in the legends). All simulations are performed at coexistence conditions (100bar and 284K). In all cases, $\varepsilon = 8k_B T$. Each color represents an independent trajectory generated using different seeds starting from the same fluid configuration.

FIG. 2. Number of water molecules in the crystal slab, n_h , as function of time for several trajectories and different well radius, r_w (as indicated in the legends). All simulations are performed at coexistence conditions (100bar and 284K). In all cases, $\varepsilon = 8k_B T$. Each color represents an independent trajectory generated using different seeds starting from the same fluid configuration.

FIG. 3. Number of water molecules in the crystal slab, n_h , as function of time for several trajectories and different well radius, r_w (as indicated in the legends). All simulations are performed at coexistence conditions (100bar and 284K). In all cases, $\epsilon = 8k_B T$. Each color represents an independent trajectory generated using different seeds starting from the same fluid configuration.

FIG. 4. Number of water molecules in the crystal slab, n_h , as function of time for several trajectories and different well radius, r_w (as indicated in the legends). All simulations are performed at coexistence conditions (400bar and 287K). In all cases, $\varepsilon = 8k_B T$. Each color represents an independent trajectory generated using different seeds starting from the same fluid configuration.

FIG. 5. Number of water molecules in the crystal slab, n_h , as function of time for several trajectories and different well radius, r_w (as indicated in the legends). All simulations are performed at coexistence conditions (1000bar and 289K). In all cases, $\varepsilon = 8k_B T$. Each color represents an independent trajectory generated using different seeds starting from the same fluid configuration.

FIG. 6. Number of water molecules in the crystal slab, n_h , as function of time for several trajectories and different well radius, r_w (as indicated in the legends). All simulations are performed at coexistence conditions (1000bar and 289K). In all cases, $\varepsilon = 8k_B T$. Each color represents an independent trajectory generated using different seeds starting from the same fluid configuration.

II. ELECTION OF THE OPTIMAL VALUE

A. Original criterion

According to the original works of Espinosa *et al.*,^{3,4} the optimal value r_w^0 is located between the highest value r_w for which none of the trajectories shows an induction period and the lowest value for which at least one trajectory exhibits an induction period. We have followed this approach in the main article to be consistent with the original method and with our previous works. The different r_w^0 values obtained following the original criterion are presented in Table I.

TABLE I. Optimal values, r_w^0 , as obtained using the original and overall behavior criteria at different pressures. All simulations are performed using $\varepsilon = 8k_B T$ and at coexistence conditions. See further details in the main text.

P (bar)	r_w^0 (Å) ^a	r_w^0 (Å) ^b	r_w^0 (Å) ^c
100	0.84(8)	0.87(8)	1.00(2)
400	0.94(8)	0.97(5)	1.03(2)
1000	0.97(8)	0.99(4)	1.04(3)

^a Original criterion.

^b Overall behavior criterion using the data from regions I and II.

^c Overall behavior criterion using only the data from region II.

Our election is motivated by reasons that can be explained using the combination of the number of water molecules in the hydrate phase as a function of time, $n_h = n_h(t)$, and the number of wells filled by water molecules as a function of time, $N_{fw} = N_{fw}(t)$. According to our previous experience on the determination of interfacial free energies of hydrates, we think the following plots could explain why we have chosen the r_w^0 values presented in the main manuscript.

Fig. 7 shows $n_h = n_h(t)$ and $N_{fw} = N_{fw}(t)$, for some trajectories at 1000bar already presented in the manuscript, that are relevant to the discussion about the existence of induction period. The discussion and results presented here are equivalent to those for 100 and 400bar. Particularly, we consider the following trajectories: trajectory without induction period using $r_w = 0.950 \text{ \AA}$ ($< r_w^0$), panels (a) and (b); trajectory with induction period using $r_w = 0.982 \text{ \AA}$ ($\sim r_w^0$), panels (c) and (d); trajectory with induction period using $r_w = 1.077 \text{ \AA}$ ($\sim r_w^0$), panels (e) and (f); and trajectory with an “infinite” induction period, i.e., trajectory that does not show crystallization during the

FIG. 7. Number of water molecules in the hydrate slab, n_h as a function of time in panels (a), (c), (e), and (g); and number of filled wells, N_{fw} , as a function of time in panels (b), (d), (f), and (h), for some trajectories using different well radius r_w (as indicated in the legends). Simulations are performed using 48 wells, with $\varepsilon = 8k_B T$, and at coexistence conditions of 1000bar and 289 K. Blue colors represent trajectories or parts of trajectories classified without induction period (hydrate growing) and red colors are trajectories or parts of trajectories in which an induction period is identified.

complete simulation (100ns) using $r_w = 1.235 \text{ \AA}$ ($> r_w^0$), panels (g) and (h). The key point of this figure is to show that the elections suggested by us make sense and are in agreement with the spirit of the original methodology. As can be clearly seen in panel (a), there is no induction period. Panel (b) shows the instantaneous number of wells filled by water molecules. The behavior of N_{fw} as a function of time is the same (within the statistical uncertainties) in the whole 100ns of the simulation. Particularly, all the wells are filled (48) and only small fluctuations are seen along the complete simulation. The mean value of $\bar{N}_{fw} \sim 47.99$ and the standard deviation is $\sigma_{\bar{N}_{fw}} \sim 0.046$. It is important to mention that all the wells of the mold are filled in the first 200ps of the simulations in all the cases considered in this work.

Panel (g) shows the opposite behavior: the system does not crystallize during the whole simulation (100ns), i.e., one can say that the system exhibits an “infinite” induction period. In other words, the free energy barrier between the hydrate phase and the aqueous solution is so high that the probability associated to a transition from the fluid phase to the hydrate phase is negligible. This behavior is reflected in panel (h) where $N_{fw}(t)$ shows a similar trend than in panel (b) but with an important difference: fluctuations of N_{fw} , $\sigma_{N_{fw}}$, are larger. According to our calculations, in this case $\sigma_{\bar{N}_{fw}} \sim 0.21$ (note that here $\bar{N}_{fw} \sim 47.88$). This happens when $r_w = 1.235 \text{ \AA}$. Why fluctuations are 4 – 5 times greater than in panel (b)? Only water molecules trapped in the wells of the mold form the thin slab of hydrate and no hydrate-like water molecules exist in the system (the system does not crystallize due to the height of the free energy barrier between the hydrate and the liquid). This provokes that a few percentage of molecules go out from some wells from time to time, increasing $\sigma_{N_{fw}}$. This does not occur in panel (b), for $r_w = 0.950 \text{ \AA}$, because the system crystallizes and the hydrate phase grows around the region at which the wells of the mold are located in the simulation box. In the same way, “the hydrate-like water molecules provide extra stability to the water molecules at the wells” reducing the $\sigma_{N_{fw}}$ value.

Panels (c) and (e) show qualitatively the same behavior: induction periods in the first 10ns of the simulation (red color) and hydrate growing (crystallization) in the rest of the simulation time (blue color). This is also corroborated by the values of fluctuations of N_{fw} in the first 10ns: $\sigma_{\bar{N}_{fw}} \sim 0.15$ in panel (d) and $\sigma_{\bar{N}_{fw}} \sim 0.19$ in panel (f) (trajectories in red color). According to panel (h), these values correspond to induction periods. And also in the rest of the simulation time: $\sigma_{\bar{N}_{fw}} \sim 0.05$ in panel (d) and $\sigma_{\bar{N}_{fw}} \sim 0.05$ in panel (f) (trajectories in blue color). According to panel (c), these values correspond to crystallization periods. Consequently, we do not see real,

qualitative, and quantitative differences between the behavior of $n_h(t)$ and $N_{fw}(t)$ in panels (c)+(d) and (e)+(f), respectively. Then, we assume that $r_w = 0.982 \text{ \AA}$ is the lowest value of r_w for which at least one trajectory exhibits induction period. Since $r_w = 0.950 \text{ \AA}$ is the highest value for which none of the trajectories shows an induction period, $r_w^0 \approx 0.966 \text{ \AA}$. This criterion is strictly the same one proposed by the authors in the original MI methodology^{3,4} and the same one we have used in this work for 100 and 400 bar and in our previous works for determining the interfacial free energy of the CO₂ hydrate^{1,2}. In order to keep the consistency with our previous works, we opt to follow the same approach for choosing the r_w^0 values.

It is also important to remark that we have also found trajectories in which $N_{fw}(t)$ behaves during a certain time like in the red regions of panels (d), (f), and (h) but the system is crystallizing, i.e., $n_h(t)$ behaves during that time like in the blue regions of panels (c), (e), and (g). These results correspond to few simulations currently in course. Taking into account only the results presented in this work, our main conclusion is that information from the behavior of $n_h(t)$ alone or from the behavior of $N_{fw}(t)$ alone is not enough to identify if a trajectory has induction period or not. We think that a careful inspection of both magnitudes, $n_h(t)$ and $N_{fw}(t)$, helps to identify in most of cases if one trajectory exhibits or not induction period. Clearly, we think that a more detailed study of this issue is necessary. This is devoted to a future work since this is out of the scope of this paper.

B. Overall behavior criterion

According to the original criterion, in combination with the careful inspection of the number of filled wells and their fluctuations, the region with large fluctuations in the mold occupancy is identified with an induction period, and consequently, with the absence of a crystal structure around the mold. According to the original methodology, this implies that the system is in an induction period prior to the overcoming of a free energy barrier. However, another interpretation is possible. The absence of crystal structure could be also interpreted as a stuck crystal growth due to the low step-like kinetics with which the hydrate apparently grows. Unfortunately, it is very difficult to distinguish between induction period and stuck growth at the beginning of the simulations in which there is absence of crystal structure.

An option could be look at the overall behavior as a function of the well radius to discriminate between both views. To this end, Fig. 8 shows the average induction period, $\langle t_{\text{ind}} \rangle$, as a function

FIG. 8. Average induction period, $\langle t_{\text{ind}} \rangle$, as a function of r_w for pressures 100 (green open diamonds), 400 (blue open squares), and 1000 bar (red open circle). The filled symbols correspond to the r_w^0 values obtained from the original criterion at 100, 400, and 1000 bar.

of r_w , identified in Figs. 1-6 for all the simulations considered in this work that exhibit possible induction periods higher than 3 ns. Data with different colors correspond to the three pressures considered in this work, 100 (green), 400 (blue), and 1000 bar (red). The filled symbols along the x -axis represent the optimal radii, r_w^0 , at each pressure obtained using the original criterion (see also Table I).

The general behavior of each series is qualitatively the same. Each pressure shows two different regions: (1) a region (I) in which $\langle t_{\text{ind}} \rangle$ is approximately constant, with $\langle t_{\text{ind}} \rangle \sim 5 - 7$ ns, for low values of r_w ; and (2) a second region (II) in which $\langle t_{\text{ind}} \rangle$ grows (approximately) linearly for high values of r_w . According to the definition of induction period, at each pressure, r_w^0 can be obtained from the overall behavior criterion extrapolating the induction period data towards zero, i.e., considering the limit $\langle t_{\text{ind}} \rangle \rightarrow 0$. However, as we have previously mentioned, two different behaviors are seen in Fig. 8. One could be tempted to discard the $\langle t_{\text{ind}} \rangle$ values of region I since these points correspond to states in which induction period and stuck growth can be confused, as we have previously mentioned. Note that these values correspond to simulations in which a possible induction period is observed according to the analysis of $n_h = n_h(t)$ (see Figs. 1-6). The behavior of the system at these states could be considered isolated events. However, this happens

FIG. 9. CO₂ hydrate–water interfacial free energy as a function of pressure along its dissociation line as obtained from the MI–H methodology using the original criterion (marron symbols), the overall behavior criterion with all the data (magenta symbols), and the overall behavior criterion with only the data from region II (dark green). The dashed lines are guides to the eye.

systematically. As can be seen in Fig. 8, these states exist at the three pressures and for several values of r_w .

To account for properly the existence of these states, we have performed two different linear fits from the data presented in Fig. 8. The first one considers all the $\langle t_{\text{ind}} \rangle$ values (regions I and II), shown by continuous lines with different colors. We have also performed a second linear fit taking into account only the $\langle t_{\text{ind}} \rangle$ values of region B, shown by dashed lines. The optimal values of r_w obtained from both linear fits have been also included in Table I. We have also studied the corresponding uncertainties using the same criterion presented in the main article.

From this information, it is possible to calculate the interfacial free energy of the hydrate, at different pressures, using both criteria. We have represented the interfacial free energy as a function of pressure in Fig. 9. We have included the results obtained from the overall behavior criterion using the the two linear fittings (including only region I and including regions I and II). We have also plotted the results obtained using the original criterion. As can be seen, the three results show the same qualitative behavior: there is a weak correlation between the interfacial energy values and the pressure, i.e., γ_{hw} slightly decreases with pressure along the dissociation line. These effect

is more pronounced when using the original criterion and the overall behavior criterion with the linear fit including the data corresponding to region I and II. Finally, it is interesting to mention that results obtained from the original and overall behavior (including data from regions I and II) criteria predict the same results within the error bars.

III. AVERAGE NUMBER OF FILLED WELLS

We have included the average number of filled wells, $\langle N_{fw}(\epsilon) \rangle_{NP_z, \mathcal{A}T}$, as a function of the well depth ϵ , at 400 and 1000 bar for the principal plane of the CO₂ hydrate. Fig. 10 shows the filling curves, at 400 bar, using a value $r_w = 1.156 \text{ \AA}$. We have also considered other values of the potential range of the wells, $r_w = 1.172, 1.188, \text{ and } 1.203 \text{ \AA}$, shown in the inset. Fig. 11 shows the filling curves, at 1000 bar, using a value $r_w = 1.203 \text{ \AA}$. We have also considered other values of the potential range of the wells, $r_w = 1.219, 1.235, \text{ and } 1.251 \text{ \AA}$, shown in the inset. Note that in all the cases $\langle N_{fw}(\epsilon) \rangle_{NP_z, \mathcal{A}T}$, as a function of time, behaves smoothly and it reaches the expected plateau value ($N_{fw} \rightarrow N_w$) when $\epsilon \rightarrow \epsilon_m$. As in the case of 100 bar (main article), all the wells of the mold are fully occupied with only one water molecule for all the values of ϵ used for the integration.

FIG. 10. Average number of filled wells, $\langle N_{fw}(\epsilon) \rangle_{NP_z \mathcal{A}T}$, as a function of the well depth ϵ , at 400 bar for the principal plane of the CO₂ hydrate. The radius of the mold used is $r_w = 1.156 \text{ \AA}$. The circles correspond to the values obtained from $NP_z \mathcal{A}T$ simulations of 40 ns and the blue curve represents its corresponding fit. The inset represents the fits of the average number of filled wells using well radii higher than the optimal value, $r_w = 1.156$ (blue), 1.172 (black), 1.188 (red), and 1.203 \AA (green).

FIG. 11. Average number of filled wells, $\langle N_{fw}(\epsilon) \rangle_{NP_z \mathcal{A}T}$, as a function of the well depth ϵ , at 1000 bar for the principal plane of the CO₂ hydrate. The radius of the mold used is $r_w = 1.203 \text{ \AA}$. The circles correspond to the values obtained from $NP_z \mathcal{A}T$ simulations of 40 ns and the blue curve represents its corresponding fit. The inset represents the fits of the average number of filled wells using well radii higher than the optimal value, $r_w = 1.203$ (blue), 1.219 (black), 1.235 (red), and 1.251 \AA (green).

IV. MULTIMEDIA CONTENT

We have included here the list of complementary multimedia results (movies) obtained from calculations performed in this work. In particular, these results correspond to Molecular Dynamics (MD) computer simulations in the $NP_z \mathcal{A}T$ ensemble starting from an initial and equilibrated liquid-liquid configuration of the CO₂ + H₂O binary mixture considered in the main paper. The movies shown here correspond to simulations carry out at 100 bar and 284 K using the Mold Integration - Host.

In our simulations, a mold of attractive sites is placed in the center of the simulation box, at the equilibrium positions of the oxygen atoms of water molecules along two principal planes of the sI structure of the CO₂ hydrate. We use $N_w = 48$ attractive interacting sites, with $\epsilon = 8 k_B T$ and two different well values: $r_w = 0.697 \text{ \AA}$, a value below the optimal radius value $r_w^0 = 0.84 \text{ \AA}$ (video-MIH-crystallization.mpg), and $r_w = 1.172 \text{ \AA}$, a value above the optimal radius value (video-MIH-no-crystallization.mpg). In the first case, the system crystallizes completely since there is no free energy barrier between the hydrate and the aqueous solution. In the second case, the system is not able to overcome the free energy barrier but is able to form a thin hydrate slab.

Red and white licorice representation corresponds to oxygen and hydrogen atoms of water, respectively. In the movies obtained using the MI-H methodology, blue and yellow spheres (van der Waals representation) correspond to carbon and oxygen atoms of CO₂, respectively. Finally, the 48 cyan spheres (van der Waals representation) correspond to the mold attractive sites using $\varepsilon = 8k_B T$ and $r_w = 0.697$ (crystallization) and 1.172 \AA (no crystallization).

Here we provide the list of the files containing the movies indicating the time simulated in each case:

- Simulation using the MI-H methodology with crystallization (100 ns):
video-MIH-crystallization.mpg.
- Simulation using the MI-H methodology without crystallization (100 ns):
video-MIH-no-crystallization.mpg.

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